

- [Did you feel it? Earthquake detected in central Kentucky](#)
- [Live updates: 6 tornadoes reported in Kentucky. Light snow follows severe storms](#)
- **MESS0038: MET 2.3 - Hurricane Nicole and Earth Spots**
- **MESS0039: MET 2.31 - ; the proof the mainstream Change Theorist Data Learning Machines are...**

MET 2.32 - Gold Level evidence found/occurred January 12, 2023 with blot echo M2.6 in Burgin, Ky with concurrent connections to New Madrid Fault Zone and near Madison county fault and a tornado warning in proximal Madison county. [Part 3]

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Best Viewed at: <http://bit.ly/3kGDW0o>

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ABSTRACT¹

In part 1 of this series, evidence was presented for a connection between Hurricane Nicole and a Nor'wester storm, as an Earth Spot², located simultaneously to Nicole's landfall, at the High Plains water table confluence in the midwest. The polarization data in terms of temperature, humidity, etc. was obviously correlated considering air doesn't penetrate the ground, but charge does. More interestingly, at the time there was no cloud cover over the regions covered in previous EGM work on the Mayfield 2021 long track tornado³, and the New Madrid Fault Zone⁴ papers⁵.

In part 2, evidence was shown that the Data Analytics+Machine Learning (DAML) systems which NOAA and windy.com use for their own "Change Theory"⁶ analytics on weather prediction, relied clearly upon known electrogeometeorological structures (EGM) with specific physical evidence⁷ and diameter sizes⁸ known, which of course correlate (also) to polar (ie - anode/cathode) behaviors. The predictions of the systems were wrong, but based on historicity. In fact the intensity of the Nicole tropical remnants were most intense not over the gravity (Bouguer) anomaly at the Big South Fork, but over the more strongly evidenced Yelverton-Hall Crooke Smile Keystone⁹; particularly at the "Jellico bend" (90 degree) of the Pine Mountain Flux. Again this was a region not covered in clouds in the event recorded in part 1.

In this paper, the author captured figures and articles, with timestamped data, and particular solar data pertaining to a series of solar flares. The resultant is an iron clad series of Platinum level (A++ grade) proof in the Davidson-Uyen¹⁰ "Earthspot" theorem of solar wind/flux→blot echo AND the Hall¹¹-Leybourne¹²-Jupp-Thornhill Theorem of the "solar forcing" mechanism. It was predicted by the late, great electrogeology founding father M. Steinbacher¹³ and the author's own work on the "Electrothermal Vine"¹⁴ connecting the Solar System Electric Circuit (Alfvenian format) to the Planetary Electric Circuit (standard model + K. Birkeland theories).

The implications and proofs in this paper cannot be overstated; it is the culmination of effect of many writers and researchers. However, for the SSEC→PEC→HEC implications it is just "another day under the sun." Climate Change modelers need to return completely to the drawing board; not the least of which reason is that the political aspects of present debunked Global Warming hacktivism¹⁵ has been exposed¹⁶, and the obviousness of the connection between the trace element level of carbon dioxide and methane, etc. have been shown to be all related to the anti-fossil-fuel lobby. As much as cigarette

¹ The AIM grade is very positive *because the evidence grade is so very positive*, indicating a "green light" for many forms of deeper research, pre-engineering, and actual engineering (disaster prevention systems, for example) on scale.

² Ben Davidson: An Introduction to Earthspots | EU2015

³ MESS0019: MET 2.1 - KY Tornado New Madrid Zone & magnetics

⁴ MESS0021: GEO 2.22 - New Madrid Zone and Blue Ridge: Magmaflux

⁵ MESS0022: GEO 2.23 - Freshwater/Groundwater table analysis vs. anomalies

⁶ MIMS - Applying Change Theory

⁷ MESS0035: A Guide to the EPEMC Trip Reports

⁸ MESS0028: GEO 2.24 - Proposed Electrogeological Scales

⁹ MESS0020: GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's Crooked Smile Hypothesis Proven by the Pine Mountain flux

¹⁰ <https://suspiciousobservers.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Paper-1.pdf>

¹¹ Andrew Hall: The Arc-Blasted Earth | EU2016

¹² Bruce Leybourne: Geometry of Earth's Endogenous Electrical Energy -- Geophysical Evidence | EU2016

¹³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/m-steinbacher>

¹⁴ HEGEME and the Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky

¹⁵ MESS0031: POS Wave of Propaganda

¹⁶ EPEMC OpEd - Peer Review Cults & Skepticism pp. 65-67

and oil company research are suspect, the political hacktivism of anti-United States adversaries (ie, socialists) has rendered their understandings of the “settled science” as, essentially, a form of blind tunnel vision. The reality is that solar forcing and the electromagnetic effects of our greater connections, given our Electric Sun¹⁷ as a now known factual reality¹⁸ accepted by the AGU¹⁹, IEEE, NOAA, and USGS, render all Climate Science previous to the 2017 September Hurricane+X-class solar flare²⁰, and to the 2021 Mayfield Tornado... and to this event as ***useless or near useless forms of theoretical, error prone data manipulation, and ergo: scientific bunk.***

The facts of this series of event are laid bare, for all to see. As Galileo said, “It moves anyways.” As Ben Shapiro made famous, “facts don’t care about your feelings.” Statistically, there is no coincidence herein... there is only scientific causation in a time-sequenced chain of events, now correlated to both known electrogeological *and* tectonic-geological structures.

In the final Section, a brief repository of Hurricane Crossing Points is considered, re: the Nicole landfall and track, potentially suggesting an important attractive node near or around the Lake Okeechobee→Orlando geographical region.

EGM Rises to the Top again

Figure 1 on the cover, displays many of the topics already previously covered by the author, elsewhere. It correlates these vectors (seems as curved because of Earth’s curvature) to four same-day events (as the solar flaring aggravation, discussed in a later section).

1. A series of intense electrical thunderstorms moving ahead of the Earthspot shown, located precisely in the pentagonal region labeled in a previous paper²¹ and known for historical earthquake intensity, within the NMFZ.
2. At the same time a mass of thunderstorm latent and saturated plasma, stretching across the expanse from there to the KY River & Lexington Fault Zone systems²²
3. Wherein at approximately 3AM, a weak and deep blot echo earthquake occurred as a “freak” incident in the USGS data, and completely alone, isolating this event from plate tectonic vectors
4. At 9am, the mass of intensity formed in the “long track zone” actually reached the Burgin, KY region, and a tornado factually appeared as the system attempted to converge a rare January event into a least-energy-spent homeostatic system, producing an EFO0/1 tornado in the Jessamine→Madison Country region, which is near and sandwiched between the faults, and historically known for powerful tornadoes.

* Please note, specifically, that the blot echo occurred en route/transit to the ultimate region where the tornado warning is occurring, and when it did so the thunderstorms stretched from the NMFZ to the LFZ.

¹⁷ [MESS0005: The Sun is Electric, Period.](#)

¹⁸ <https://now.uiowa.edu/2021/07/physicists-led-university-iowa-more-fully-describe-suns-electric-field>

¹⁹ <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Electric+Currents+in+Geospace+and+Beyond-p-9781119324492>

²⁰ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1029/2018SW001897>

²¹ Mess 19, Ibid. p.6

²² http://www.uky.edu/KGS/pdf/mc20_12.pdf

Figure 2 - 3 AM Earth spot visible just west of the NMFZ, in the Ozark geological region. Which itself has plasma petroglyphs²³ and *may* be electrogeological. It's not been conjectured as of yet, by the author or anyone else to his knowledge to be EGM related. One issue difficult to surmount is it would seem to the author that the fluorspar district + Land Between the Lakes + Hicks' Dome/Garden of the Gods²⁴ EGM formation would be more genesis related in terms of tornados. However, they definitely form in the Arkansas' crystal matrix southwest-proximal to the NMFZ.; credit: Windy.com

* Note the temperature inflection before the front and behind it, ~1/3 that of the Nicole/Nor'wester system event.

²³ <https://mostateparks.com/page/77856/petroglyphs>

²⁴ [Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge](#) pp.6-9

Figure 3 - Burgin, KY blot echo at 35.3 km deep; 3 am EST local time; credit: USGS

Will... of Lexington crosses East Main Street during a rain storm in downtown Lexington, Ky., on Thursday, Jan. 12, 2023. Ryan C. Hermens rhermens@herald-leader.com

TORNADO WARNING EXTENDED IN MADISON COUNTY

9:42 a.m. - The **tornado warning** issued for Madison County has been extended to at least 10:15 a.m., according to the NWS.

The warning also included southeastern Clark County, the NWS said. The storm will be near Harris Ferry around 9:50 a.m., according to the NWS.

Tornado Warning including Richmond KY and Union City KY until 10:15 AM EST pic.twitter.com/fGuhoTJWJl

— NWS Louisville (@NWSLouisville) [January 12, 2023](#)

Figure 4 - Tornado reporting re: Madison County, KY and Clark County.

It may be of interest to the reader to know that the author has witnessed the attraction of supercells to this region by witnessing an EF1 before, just after work. It was just south of the KY River fault zone, between Richmond and Berea, in 2018. The supercell was well formed, and the sun was bright elsewhere. No discoloration reported. This was previous to the author's involvement in EG/EGM research. The date would be hard to find/research, but might be done in a MESSr format, elsewhere as a redux for this paper and other MESSy work.

Solar Data

January 10

Solar wind

speed: **405.6** km/sec
density: **5.44** protons/cm³
more data: [ACE](#), [DSCOVR](#)
Updated: Today at 1147 UT

X-ray Solar Flares

6-hr max: **X1** 2247 UT Jan10
24-hr: **X1** 2247 UT Jan10
[explanation](#) | [more data](#)
Updated: Today at: 2350 UT

January 11

Solar wind

speed: **409.8** km/sec
density: **7.01** protons/cm³
more data: [ACE](#), [DSCOVR](#)
Updated: Today at 1146 UT

X-ray Solar Flares

6-hr max: **C8** 2100 UT Jan11
24-hr: **M5** 0156 UT Jan11
[explanation](#) | [more data](#)
Updated: Today at: 2350 UT

January 12

Solar wind

speed: **401.5** km/sec
density: **6.47** protons/cm³
more data: [ACE](#), [DSCOVR](#)
Updated: Today at 0546 UT

X-ray Solar Flares

6-hr max: **M1** 1457 UT Jan12
24-hr: **M1** 0650 UT Jan12
[explanation](#) | [more data](#)
Updated: Today at: 1750 UT

Daily Sun: 10 Jan 23

Expand: [labels](#) | [no labels](#)

Sunspots AR3181, 82 and 84 all pose a threat for [X-class](#) solar flares. Credit: SDO/HMI

Sunspot number: 142

Updated 10 Jan 2023

Daily Sun: 11 Jan 23

Expand: [labels](#) | [no labels](#)

Sunspots AR3181, 82, 84 and 86 all pose a threat for [M](#) to [X-class](#) solar flares. Credit: SDO/HMI

Sunspot number: 201

Updated 11 Jan 2023

Daily Sun: 12 Jan 23

Expand: [labels](#) | [no labels](#)

Sunspots AR3181, 82, 84 and 86 have unstable magnetic fields that pose a threat for [M](#) to [X-class](#) solar flares. Credit: SDO/HMI

Sunspot number: 183

Updated 12 Jan 2023

Figures 5 - 7 all indicate solar sunspot location for the day and the two days previous when the first X-class solar flares of 2023 occurred. Since then the system has produced a "killshot" CME which was not directed at the Earth. Credit: spaceweather.com

* The effects of these flares can arrive in hours; often the material may take days. It's probable that the Jan 10 was etymological for this January 12th event. Please note the Firday 13th the following day held "true to form" for a Friday the 13th and was, clinically speaking, a 'cluster' of bizarre behaviors and conditions reported, as well as technical problems. None seemed related to Templars, or social norms/expectations, and so the solar data is most likely the vector.

Figure 8 - Comparison map, note the green arrow is the tornado warning area; and the Mayfield incident is 2021 related, but a good indicator of the outer edge (where a gravity anomaly is located). The above was created with Google Earth to eliminate the curvature, and this shows the straight vector relationship outlined above, with the present data.; credit: Google Earth/author

Taking a Nullschool Run at it.

Figure 9 - Based on the MESSy on the “Spheres of Heaven”, we see that the most important region for the electric activity is in the Thermosphere; and this is because it is conduction, while the Mesosphere and Exosphere are dielectric. Meanwhile, of course, the stratosphere is also conductive, but has a dielectric region, and the Troposphere is where thunderstorms are.

Note the km of the layers, which will be important in the Nullschool captured hPa data.

<https://earth.nullschool.net>

Figure 10 - the Earthspot is best seen at the 250 hPa layer, which correlates to 10.3 km²⁵. Looking at Figure 9, this is the **exact boundary region of the Troposphere**.

This doesn't prove the Earthspot only shows up at the boundary. It just proves it *is* at the boundary.

Wind is the motion of ionic (plasma) charges. Wind is electric. It does produce a magnetic field. Animals frequently use these fields and electric fields generated by the PEC and climate, to migrate or even cross long distances. It would be ridiculous to not think that an electric motor like a supercell would not be affected by EM systems, let alone the Electric Sun!

²⁵ https://www.weather.gov/epz/wxcalc_pressurealtitude

Figure 11 - At the 25 km (stratospheric) level, we see the large Birkeland Currents that affect the polar wind currents at the north and south pole. Here we do not see such a current in the affected area; but we do see it in the Gulf Stream region (probably supplying the charge source of heat for the GS), and we see a boundary connecton at the region mentioned for Hurricane Nicole. But nothing, in particular, stands out for our present study area. However, please note the overall wind direction is counter to most of the air mass motion in the study, and often present as such in “odd” days. Typically it should want to move southwest to northeast. Not on Jan. 12, 2023! credit: Nullschool

Figure 12 - Nullschool's modeling of the Earthspot at 3 am UTC is a bit behind. May suggest a CST timing, or some delay. Nevertheless, there is very good resolution on the data at 5.5 km elevation.

* Note the negative (cathode) Earthspot propositional at the aforementioned Gulf Stream, near the Florida Keys. It is **not clear** if the two systems are directly related or only through the PEC synchronous field. Air is compressible, so the synchronous field is not 1:1 deformable, and the interaction of systems is not in a linear relationship, as the geometers might suggest. A turbulent flow precludes all the laminar assumptions in symmetric modeling, and requires a nonlinear and potentially fractalian geometry.

Figure 13 - At the Stratospheric level, at 9 am, we see that the most intense storm is *not* in the region where the tornado is. It is particularly in the region where the earthquake/blot echo occurred. (see red/yellow). The Earthspot appears to be located east of the Ozark region.

Figure 14 (gif) - Animation from windy.com with storm recall from 3 am to 4 pm. Note that the storm at 9 am stretches from the NMSZ; with peaks at the zone, and at the anomalies. Note the peak activity at 1 pm at the Daniel Boone National Forest leyline.

When we see the resulting “explosion” of full statewide rain by afternoon, one has to wonder if there was some form of ‘grounding’ that occurred once the tornado vortex system connects the atmospheric energy to the ground system. Let us look, interestingly, at what the “I Ching” has said, in the past, about the type of soothing rain that comes after energy has built up:

“3. Chun / Difficulty at the Beginning

above K’AN - THE ABYSMAL, WATER

below CHÊN - THE AROUSING, THUNDER

*The name of the hexagram, Chun, really connotes a blade of grass pushing against an obstacle as it sprouts out of the earth--hence the meaning, "difficulty at the beginning." The hexagram indicates the way in which heaven and earth bring forth individual beings. It is their first meeting, which is beset with difficulties. The lower trigram Chên is the Arousing; its motion is upward and its image is thunder. The upper trigram K'an stands for the Abysmal, the dangerous. Its motion is downward and its image is rain. The situation points to teeming, chaotic profusion; thunder and rain fill the air. But the **chaos clears up**. While **the Abysmal sinks**, the upward movement eventually passes beyond the danger. A **thunderstorm brings release from tension, and all things breathe freely again.**"²⁶*

²⁶ http://www2.unipr.it/~deyoung/I_Ching_Wilhelm_Translation.html

Hurricane Crossing Zone²⁷

Figures 15 - 18; credit: wikipedia.com/NOAA

Hurricane Jeane (2004)

Hurricane Ian (2022)

Hurricane Charlie (2004)

Hurricane Nicole (2022)

It would be interesting to find the solar data for these events, and place them in a separate MESSr.

²⁷ Credit to J. Kines for the presearch in this, and finding the weather reports.

Consider the following overlay:

Figure 19 - Observe the Orlando crossing point, such as it is; for which is proposed that there is an electrical cause, which the hurricane (electrovortex) is attempting to achieve a form of ground equilibrium.

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